

THE EFFECT OF TOUGHENING ON THE FRACTURE BEHAVIOUR OF A

GLASS-FIBRE REINFORCED POLYAMIDE

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Summary

A range of short glass fibre reinforced nylon 6.6 compounds containing dispersions of a rubber phase have been subjected to mechanical and impact testing. The fracture morphology has also been studied. The results show that the mechanical properties may be modified by the rubber addition in a predictable manner. Stiffness and strength are both reduced and at low fibre fractions only there is increase in ductility. However, at glass contents exceeding 20% V_f the rubber containing material is no more ductile than that with just the glass reinforcement. The rubber reinforced grades show improved toughness under impact tests and it appears that this is due to a modification of the mode of crack propagation. It was observed that a characteristic form of sheathed pull-out occurred in these materials. This was confined to fractures formed at high loading rates. At low loading rates the performance of the rubber toughened material was only marginally better.

Introduction

Short glass-fibre reinforced thermoplastics (SGFTP) have been used in many commercial applications where their enhanced stiffness and strength may be exploited. An unfortunate feature of the reinforcement, however, is that, whilst stiffness and strength may be quite dramatically increased, ductility and toughness are usually reduced. Several thermoplastics materials have been produced in which toughness is enhanced by the introduction of a dispersion of an elastomeric or rubbery phase into the base material. This technique has been applied in the main to the amorphous glassy, brittle materials, eg polystyrene, but has more recently been shown to be effective in the semi crystalline polyamide thermoplastics. These materials are commonly brittle when dry but become tougher and more ductile when plasticised by absorption of water from the atmosphere. The rubber dispersion gives a more controllable increase in toughness. In the present work the effect of the combination of fibre reinforcement and rubber toughening has been studied in a single grade of polyamide 6.6.

Several workers have studied the mechanisms of rubber toughening and fibre reinforcement separately but little has been published on their combined effect. Mandell and McGarry (1) and Lhymm and Schultz (2) have studied crack propagation in SGFTPs. They conclude that the toughness of these materials is influenced mainly by the process of fibre pull out which occurs as the crack propagates through the matrix. Small additions of fibre appear to reduce both ductility and toughness because there is insufficient fibre to either reinforce or contribute to the pull out process. However with larger proportions of fibre, although the ductility tends to be further decreased, the toughness is observed to increase. The overall toughness is a function of both the strength of the material and its ability to participate in energy dissipating mechanisms such as pull out.

Experimental

Materials

The range of short glass fibre reinforced nylons under study were all prepared from a single batch of polyamide 6.6, chopped E-glass fibres and a suitable rubber compound. These materials were dry blended in the appropriate proportions, and passed through a conventional precompounding extruder to produce granules for injection moulding. A range of materials was prepared to give fibre fractions up to 30% by volume with rubber contents of 0, 5, 10 and 20% by weight of polyamide. The rubber employed was a hydrocarbon elastomer which was dispersed throughout the nylon matrix during the precompounding extrusion.

Double-feed gated flat plaques, 150 x 150 x 3 mm, were prepared by injection moulding. These plaques were then machined into the range of testpieces for mechanical testing. All the materials were dried prior to injection moulding and stored under dessication at all times until tested.

Mechanical Testing

Various mechanical tests were carried out on the testpieces machined from the plaques. These included tensile and plane strain compression tests to identify the fundamental material properties, together with several toughness tests. Impact testing has been carried out using both Charpy and an instrumented falling weight impact test. Fracture toughness tests were carried out using an ASTM type compact tension test specimen of 75 x 75 x 3 mm.

Microscopy

A number of fracture surfaces were examined by scanning electron microscopy.

Results and Discussion

Tensile properties

Testpieces machined from the plaques were tested on an Instron testing machine using a strain gauge extensometer. The gauge portion was 12 x 3 mm cross section and 100 mm long. They were tested at a cross head speed of 1 mm/min which approximates to a strain rate of $1.7 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

Young's Modulus

The stiffness of all the materials was proportional to the fibre fraction (Figure 1). The reinforcement efficiency of glass fibres in the various rubber filled materials was, however, quite different. In the polyamide 66 with no rubber the stiffness is improved by a factor of 7, over 0-30% V_f . In the rubber toughened materials it was much lower, and at 20% wt fraction of rubber the reinforcement factor is only 3 over a similar V_f range. The fibre length distributions are thought to be similar in all materials so this suggests that the shear stress developed at the fibre matrix interface must be significantly less in the rubber containing materials.

Figures 1 and 2: Tensile Young's modulus and strength vs. glass fibre fraction.

Strength

The strength of polyamide 66 composites (Figure 2) is not linearly proportional to the fibre fraction, and this effect is well known (3,4). The departure from linearity at higher volume fractions ($>12\% V_f$) is attributable to the increase in overlapping stress fields brought about by increasing the proximity of the fibres, giving rise to debonding and penny-shaped cracks in tension. This effect is observed in both the polyamide 66 and the rubber toughened (RT) matrix materials. The rubber particles reduce the strength of the matrix in proportion to their concentration and they are consequently weaker materials at all fibre fractions, and show a greater departure from linearity. The 20% wt RT polyamide 66 in fact reaches maximum strength at approximately 22% glass. This suggests that the interaction zones may be more extensive in the rubber modified material. It should be noted that fibre reinforcement, over the ranges studied, leads to increases in both stiffness and strength. The capacity of the material to store elastic strain energy in thereby increased and this must influence its toughness.

Strain to failure

Embrittlement of all the materials is shown to be severe at higher fibre fractions (Figure 3). The effect is most severe in the rubber toughened materials which exhibit much higher matrix ductility. It is of interest that all the curves fall to a value of 2.5 - 2.0% elongation at fibre fractions greater than 20%. It can be seen that the unmodified polyamide 66 may even give marginally more ductile composites at high fibre fractions.

Figure 3: Tensile ultimate strains vs. fibre fraction showing losses in ductility.

Compression Tests

The plane strain compression test described by and applied to polymers by Williams (5) has been used to measure yield stresses (Figure 4). This configuration is less sensitive to flaw induced brittle failure which limits the tensile strength at the higher fibre fractions, and is an extremely useful method of obtaining a geometry independent "true yield stress".

The graphs of yield stress versus fibre concentration are a family of parallel straight lines. These indicate yield strength is increased by fibre addition to a similar extent in all materials, independent of the rubber content. This is in marked contrast to the trends observed for both modulus and tensile strength.

Figure 4: Geometry independent yield stresses are proportional to glass and rubber contents.

Charpy Impact Tests

The impact toughness as measured by the Charpy test (Figure 5) highlights the virtues of rubber toughening in short glass fibre reinforced polyamide 66. The toughness is significantly increased for all rubber toughened grades. The matrix impact toughness is actually reduced by small fibre additions. The extent of this embrittlement has not been studied in detail but is reported elsewhere (3,4,6) and suggests that the fibres provide internal "flaws" which provide crack initiation sites. Despite this embrittlement the toughness of the rubber modified grades is always above that of the unmodified polyamide. At higher fibre fractions improvements in toughness are observed. (The data presented are for testpieces with machine cut notches in which the extent of this improvement is less than with moulded testpieces (6).) Inspection of the fracture surfaces confirms that this higher toughness may be associated with extensive fibre pull out. The matrix ductility is suppressed in all materials at high strain rates, as may

be observed in Figure 6. However, some mechanism of toughening must be operative in the RT grades to account for their superior impact performance. The fracture surfaces of the RT composites have revealed many pulled out fibres which are coated in a well developed adherent sheath of matrix. This effect (Figure 7) is reproducible in all RT grades and undoubtedly contributes to their toughness. A comparison of Figures 6 and 7 indicates the much greater matrix involvement in the RT material. The proportions of the fibre "sheath" are a function of the rubber content. At 20% wt rubber sheaths of up to 5 μm thick have been observed, and correspondingly less at lower rubber contents, although the sheath thickness is also strain rate and temperature dependent. This sheathing phenomenon was found to occur only at the higher strain rates (ie impact tests). It did not occur in the compact tension fracture tests (- see for example Figure 11).

Figure 5: Charpy pendulum impact energies vs. glass fibre fraction.

Instrumented Falling Weight Tests

The data presented for instrumented falling weight impact testing (Figures 8 and 9) are for the unmodified and 20% rubber grades only. The trends observed in the total energy of break results are similar to those

Figure 6: A typical glass fibre reinforced nylon 6.6 impact fracture surface revealing a brittle matrix with clearly pulled out fibres.

Figure 7: 20% RT nylon 6.6 impact fracture surfaces. The matrix has failed in a brittle though more granular texture than the material containing no rubber (Figure 6). The fibres are coated in an adherent sheath of matrix.

for the Charpy test. The test geometry is, however, very different, and the test specimen is unnotched, so actual energy values cannot be compared. The rubber toughened grade absorbs more than twice as much the energy as the unmodified. However, the crack initiation energies for these materials are virtually identical at fibre contents greater than 15%. Only at very low V_f is the rubber modified grade superior. Clearly the rubber is effective in increasing the energy of crack propagation but not that of initiation. The role of the rubber in unfilled matrices is to initiate multiple crazing. Thus it might be expected that the crack initiation phase might not be impeded. This trend has been confirmed by a "staircase" test in which the drop weight energy was varied to obtain a threshold value for crack initiation (Figure 10). In this test no significant crack propagation was allowed to occur. The results show a very low initiation threshold for the rubber modified material at higher fibre fractions.

INSTRUMENTED FALLING WEIGHT RESULTS

CRACK INITIATION STAIRCASE RESULTS

Figures 8 and 9: The effect of fibre fraction upon the instrumented falling weight impact total break and crack initiation energies.

Figure 10: The crack initiation energies as measured by the falling weight staircase test.

Fracture Toughness Tests

The compact tension specimens were cut so that the crack would propagate across the melt flow direction. This is also the direction of fibre alignment, at least near the surface, consequently the crack propagation was not always planar and tended to turn into the flow direction. This accounts for some inaccuracies in the strain energy release rate (G) values, and in extreme cases of non-planar propagation the results were ignored. The G vs. V_f behaviour (Figure 10) was of the same general form as the Charpy, but with the following exceptions:-

- (i) The matrix values are relatively much higher; this is to be expected as the slower rate of strain allows ductile flow of the matrix even in the non-rubber grades.
- (ii) At the higher fibre fractions there is relatively less difference between RT and untoughened materials. This is most probably due to the fact that the sheath formation mode does not appear to operate at the lower strain rates associated with this test. A typical fractograph showing "clean" fibre pull out and ductile matrix behaviour is shown in Figure 11. Overall the RT grade is still significantly better than the untoughened in this test.

Figure 11: The strain energy release rates (G) as a function of fibre content.

Figure 12: A slow rate of strain fracture toughness test fracture surface for 20% RT nylon 6.6 composites. The ductility of the matrix is very pronounced and the fibres have pulled out clearly.

Stress intensity factors (K_Q) were also calculated from these tests and show that the rubber toughened polyamides are again showing greater toughness (Figure 12). The curves plotted suggest a toughness maximum at fibre fractions from 20-30%, increasing with higher rubber content. These K values correlate quite well with values calculated from E (measured in tensile test) and G , using the well known relationship:

$$K^2 = \frac{E \cdot G}{(1 - \nu)} \quad \dots (1)$$

Table 1

NYLON 6.6				RT NYLON 6.6			
V_f	E (GPa)	G (kJm^{-2})	K_{CALC} (MN/m)	V_f	E (GPa)	G (kJm^{-2})	K_{CALC} (Mn/m)
10%	6.5	2	4.6	10%	3	25	11.2
20%	10.5	3	7.25	20%	4.5	11	28.9
30%	14	4	9.66	30%	6	10	10

Table of K_{CALC} values from Equation 1.

Figure 13: Stress intensity factor vs. fibre fraction.

The size of the plastic or process zone at the crack tip has been given by the equation (8):

$$r_p = \frac{1}{2\pi} \left(\frac{K_I}{\sigma_y} \right)^2 \quad \dots (2)$$

These have been calculated and are shown in Figure 13.

The values obtained compare well with published data (1,7). The values show a very similar trend to that of the tensile strain-to-failure (Figure 3), which is not altogether surprising. Moore and Leach (7) use a term called the "Ductility Factor" which is derived from this quantity and could be taken literally as the extent of ductility. This parameter is often used to indicate the size of the plastic zone relative to the testpiece dimensions. In the present case we cannot show any experimental evidence to indicate the actual plastic zone diameter. However the notional values do indicate it to be significantly greater than the testpiece thickness (3 mm) at the lower fibre fractions. It is thus probable that the K values do not represent the true plane strain values for the material.

The rubber toughened matrix appears to be effectively embrittled at glass contents greater than 20% for all levels of rubber content. The results show that beyond 20% V_f there is little merit in using rubber toughening to influence K and G ; the polyamide 6.6 materials are stiffer and stronger. The rubber toughened materials do however exhibit better impact toughness.

Figure 14: The nominal process zone sizes calculated from the Brown and Sawley equation (8).

Microscopy

An investigation was carried out into the rubber particle morphology in the matrix in order to try to understand the sheath formation mechanism. Using etching techniques described by Wu (9) the rubber particles appear to be uniformly dispersed throughout the matrix. Preliminary observations seem to show that the rubber particles do not segregate preferentially at the fibre/matrix interface, neither do they avoid this region. Particles have also been observed in the sheath; consequently any hypothesis which is based on rubber segregation may be discounted. Further work into this study is being carried out in order to confirm these trends which are at present purely subjective because of the uncertainty of the etching technique.

The effect of increasing the rubber content is to induce thicker sheaths, as is shown in the series of SEMs (figures 15-17), and the influence upon the toughness was observed to be beneficial.

Comments on Toughness

It is clear from these studies that toughness in SF RTP materials is associated with the fibre pull out phenomenon. Toughness is observed to be greater when either gross matrix ductility (figure 11) or the sheathed type of pull out occurs. The pull out process is, however, a crack propagation effect and does not influence the crack initiation stage of fracture. This is much more dependent on the combination of stiffness and strength of the material which determines its relative capacity to store elastic strain energy. The influence of the rubber dispersion appears to be linked to this

Figure 15

Figure 16

Figure 17

Figures 15 (5% nylon 6.6), 16 (10% RT nylon 6.6) and 17 (20% RT nylon 6.6) show the increase in pull out sheath with rubber addition.

sheathed pull out and it was noted that it operated only at high rates of strain. Thus the rubber was effective in increasing the resistance to crack propagation under impact conditions but not under slow rates of loading. The effectiveness of the rubber was also reduced at the higher glass fibre loadings. In fact although useful toughening of the glass filled grades may be achieved with the rubber dispersion, this in no way matches the dramatic improvements achieved in the unreinforced grades.

The reasons for the sheathed pull out phenomenon at high strain rates are not fully understood (10). Clearly the rubber dispersion lowers the shear strength of the matrix, as is apparent from the plane strain compression data, and if the matrix is considered to be bonded strongly to the fibre then it is possible to visualise a shear failure path away from the interface. This, however, does not explain the fact that clean separation at the interface occurs at low strain rates. We believe that the slow pull out process must involve some sort of peeling mechanism by which the matrix separates from the fibre surface, and that this is inhibited at high strain rates. However, in tests over a range of elevated temperatures (designed to soften the matrix) and both high and low strain rates we have been unable to produce the sheathed pull out effect in nylons which did not contain rubber.

Conclusions

The mechanical properties of a range of short fibre reinforced nylon 6.6 compounds with 0-20% additions of a rubber dispersion have been prepared and subjected to mechanical and impact tests. These show that the addition of rubber reduces the stiffness and strength of the fibre reinforced materials and generally increases their toughness.

The addition of the rubber does not change the overall effect of glass reinforcement. That is, ductility is reduced and impact toughness is first reduced and then enhanced as the quantity of glass is increased. The rubber toughened grades always showed better impact performance than those containing only glass.

The toughness enhancement brought about by the use of rubber is associated with a modification of the fracture mode, whereby sheathes of matrix are pulled out with the fibres. This effect is only observed in high rate tests and it is noteworthy that the rubber additions do not significantly enhance toughness in low straight tests.

As in all SFRTPs the additions of the fibres increases the stiffness and strength of the material but the ductility is very severely reduced. This effect persists in the rubber containing materials which are much more ductile at low glass contents, but indistinguishable from the non-rubber containing material at the high fibre fractions. It would appear that toughness, or resistance to fracture, depends on a complex interaction between stiffness and strength and energy absorbing mechanisms such as fibre pull out. The former influence the crack initiation stage to a greater extent whilst the latter are dominant in the crack propagation stage.

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